

POLICY BRIEF

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THE CHALLENGES OF THE SOCIAL JUSTICE ISSUES FOR THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION IN THE AGENDA OF THE BRICS

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POLICY STATEMENT

The BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) consolidated itself as a possible economic bloc of international cooperation during 2000. The bank Goldman Sachs was the first to categorize the BRICS countries as promising markets for economic and finance agents' operation. However, in 2008, with the global financial crises that reach the US and Europe, the discussion about the role of the BRICS becomes relevant. The crises emphasized the significant countries' economic fragilities and reduced their powers face to the new world order. In 2009, the first summit of the BRICS in Russia with the presence of the chiefs of the state of the five countries, with annual summits since then. At the current time, the BRICS try to consolidate an agenda of discussion beyond the market identity. The thematic that should be strengthened in the BRICS agenda is Social Justice. If we think in the post COVID10 pandemic, the vulnerable population's social and economic impacts will be, no doubt, the most negatives.

BACKGROUND

The economic growth of the BRICS does not indicate the better well-being of its population. In the BRICS the poverty, the lack of access to the basic infrastructure, low education, and other indicators of the significant part of the population; request that the countries support public policies that promote more equity in the international sphere. Russia has historical roots of inequalities, with the Gini Coefficient changeable and average income disproportionate between the economic sectors. On the other hand, despite its competitiveness in technology, India is considered a country with extreme inequalities (Income, wealth, capacities, choices); adding to these, the country envisages the Castes system and severe discrimination based on gender. Despite its economic success, based on the modern industry, China has a traditional rural system, interpersonal inequalities, territorial inequalities to the access of health and education. South Africa is a country with roots in interracial issues, class, gender, territorial, and presents the lowest tax of the participation of the youth in higher education (15%) compared to the other countries. For instance, we cannot forget that Brazil has territorial inequalities and territorial denseness of industries, innovation, and employment in the South and Southeast that keep the educational institutions' cyclical inequalities and unequal distribution. (IPEA, 2014)

FINDINGS

The BRICS can improve their economic and social indicators and employ social justice and solidarity as foreign policy instruments. Efforts are being made to overcome social inequalities, mainly with the support of the countries and non-governmental organizations' social programs. For example, Brazil aiming to get a permanent place at CSNU, became more proactive, mainly when assumed the mission of peace in Haiti (MINUSTAH) and the mediation of Iran's nuclear accord with Western countries. The Brazilian geostrategic zone was broadened to South America and Africa (priority regions in Brazilian cooperation actions (SUYAMA; WAISBICH; LEITE, 2016). The BRICS Summit Declaration 2018 in Joanesburgo highlighted health, education, and social development to constitute new social agents. The development of skills to capacity the citizen is between the main themes of the Declaration of 2018, including the decrease of poverty (NETSWERA et al., 2020).

However, the construction of one base to overcome the inequalities needs the support of the countries' civil society, both in the organization and execution of policies that follow the interest and necessity of the agents. In this sense, as researchers and policymakers, we must stimulate the BRICS's governments to think about the "Endurable limits of the inequalities." Who has the right to become a beneficiary of society's resources? Who determines the political and symbolic boundaries to make social justice? The answers to such issues only will appear from a deep discussion about values, perceptions, attitudes, and opinions related to the social inequalities, with the basis of the most vulnerable population in the BRICS. As SCHWARTZMAN and REIS (2004) show, each society has social codes that legitimize or delegitimize the idea of equality and inequality. In that regard, to invest in bilateral agreements that consider social justice in the BRICS, it is necessary to recognize that the sense given to equality/inequality is socially built and shared by the population. That is why we have to recognize that Public Policies that do not consider the values and padrones of society's behavior are policies designated to fail.

Once that the cooperation agenda of the BRICS aims the economic development is necessary that the civil society in the countries demand the inclusion of an ample discussion about social and human development, since the growth of the marginalization of the poor. The study of the problems related to social justice, sustainability, and gender equality find a place in the recommendations discussed in the Academic Forums about the BRICS.

There is great potential in the collaborative policies between the BRICS, but there is suspicion from the civil society because it is a "Western invention." Another problem in the current conjuncture is the emptying of the discussions about the constancy of the cooperation between the BRICS. It is possible that in the post COVID10 pandemic, the five countries re-evaluate their strategies to retake economic development. On the other hand, we hope more engaging from civil society requesting that in the economic agenda appear the discussion about alternatives of cooperation related to social inequalities, because the economic development itself will not change the marginalized population's scenery.

CONCLUSIONS

Although the BRICS countries have a common agenda that points to the reinforcement of its market, it is essential to highlight that the economic growth without social justice, sustainable model of development, and life quality to the citizens, can potentially increase the social and economic problems in the societies. In that regard, it would be a great start if the government in the BRICS countries encourage the think tanks, Academia, and members of civil society to build cultural bridges to better enforcement of the public policies to reduce the social inequalities.

SUGGESTIONS

- Goals to gender equality in the agenda of development of the BRICS nations. In the agenda, it is urgent to highlight the right to advocacy in economic resources, job access, income equity, women empowerment in different issues, etc.
- Organization of a big data/data set: A unified methodology to measure and update the primary information in/between the countries. The big data can produce annual reports and used by the Think Tanks to analyze social justice, sustainable development, and life quality in the BRICS.
- Prevent the effects of poverty on education. Poverty impacts the permanency of the children in the schools: for example, parental unemployment, child maltreatment, lack of appropriate homes and educational models, among other problems, can affect the educational development of the children.
- Commitment to guarantee of education with quality, inclusive and equitable: the BRICS nation has to ensure that all boys and girls conclude their unpaid primary and secondary education, equitable, quality, and relevant in terms of apprenticeship. Attention to the acute gender inequalities in the access to the school, mainly for girls.
- Assure universal and unpaid health to the population. Although the health field is a complex issue to consolidate some commitment between the BRICS, they should at least dialogue about which services are indispensable to protect their population's health.
- Social protection is an essential axis to the debate because the BRICS nations have to develop a strategy in the short and long term to eradicate poverty and unemployment, promised in the document of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.
- The BRICS have to ensure that until 2030 the population will have access to suitable and safe habitation, sustainable public transportation, and public green space, mainly for women and children, the elderly, and people with some disability.
- Support the culture to empower the local communities and to provide social justice in a sustainable format. This axis requires investment in the long term and protects the culture of the Afro-descendants and indigenous people.

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